

IMPORTANT ROLE OF ICT IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE EDUCATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DR. C.V. RAMAN UNIVERSITY KOTA BILASPUR – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study of library and information science (LIS) Education With special reference to Dr. C.V. Raman University Kota Bilaspur – A case study and information communication technologies (ICT).

ICT has shown a great impact on the services of the libraries. Today libraries are using it for better services and fulfill the user needs. The use of ICT has greatly revolutionized the ways in which information can be accessed by all those in need today technology is becoming a powerful tools for communication and as a mean research for learning in Education area role of the teacher training in the process of Educational innovation and the Implementation of ICT.

ICT in library and information science Education it moved to more student centered learning as world is moving rapidly toward digital information Universities need ICT based library and information science (LIS) Curriculum and to adopt to modern web technology. Library and information science (LIS) education and skill in the knowledge Era.

The paper focus use of E-library Resources by student, researcher library staff, non teaching staff faculty members of Dr. C.V. Raman University Kota, Bilaspur.

Information Communication Technologies (ICT) facilitate the process of identification, storing, processing of identification, collection and dissemination of information.

The library and information science professional are utilizing ICT to keep pace with the problem of information explosion.

KEYWORDS: *ICT, library and information science (LIS) Education, Dr. C.V. Raman University Kota Bilaspur–A case study, E-library and services*

INTRODUCTION

Dr. C.V. Raman University in Bilaspur is one of the best leading private universities in India which is devoted to achieve excellence in education in research. The Dr. C. V. Raman university Bilaspur Chhattisgarh is a premium university that maintains a unique pedagogy and innovative teaching methodology.

ESTABLISHED

This university is located in Kargi Road Kota Bilaspur (C.G.) and Established on 3

November 2006 by all India society for electronic and computer technology, under section-2 (f) of the university grant commission (UGC) Act- 1956. It is named after the first noble laureate of the country Dr. C.V. Raman.

Dr. C.V. Raman University (CVRU) is premier University of the state of Chhattisgarh with its 26 Departments including education in the field of its various faculties of library and information science, commerce, management, Law, journalism & mass, communication, engineering, IT, Research, Education, Physical education etc. through its numerous courses by an enrolment of huge number of students. The University established in the tribal region of the rural environment of Chhattisgarh with its primary objective and vision of providing higher education to the students of rural background giving an access for them to obtain an easy opportunity for getting an advanced ICT based technological studies contributing to the higher education enhancement Recognized by UGC and approved by AICTE, NCTE, Accredited by NAAC with B+ Grade, Listed in top 200 universities in NIRF by MHRD, BCI as well as certified by ISO:9001:2008, being a member of AIU, the institutional vision of this University reflect upon various initiatives to provide literal, legal, managerial and scientific knowledge to the students generating high morals, ethics and values with cultural heritage in them by helping the society in nation building through nurturing and strengthening the young talents for being the trust-worthy citizens of tomorrow.

DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY & INFORMATION SCIENCE

Dr. C. V. Raman university used to run total 26 departments in various faculties. Department of library and information science is one of them. This department was established in 2012. This department runs bachelor degree programme (B.Lib., I.Sc.) Master degree programme (M.Lib., I.Sc.) and M.Phil and Ph.D. Programme is also run by the department of library and information science of Dr. C. V. Raman university. Being situated in a rural area so many people is getting benefitted by tacking education from this institution ware not able to take higher education. Who previously due to lack of good academic institutions in the vicinity highly qualified, talented staff is teaching in this department. For the overall development of students department is conducting educational tour for students to learn about the fractioning of library system. Many co-curriculum activities are arranged for student time to time.

PURPOSE /OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY AREAS

The purpose of this study is to analyse what is happening at university recording the integration and use of ICT and examine teachers perceptions about what teaching and learning process can be improved through the use of ICT.

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

- To introduce about J.P., Choubey central library in Kota, Bilaspur (C.G.)
- To identify the use of electronic resources and application of ICT in functional libraries.
- To provide faculty with access to curriculum based information and professional development materials.
- This study or survey is limited to Dr. C.V. Raman University, Kota, Bilaspur (C.G.)

CONCEPT OF ICT

ICT has been defined as an electronic technology. It is used for collecting storing processing and communicating information. ICT infrastructure is usually considered with respect to its main areas like computer, hardware, software, and telecommunication and library and information science (LIS) Education. ICT is changing the work of libraries and information centers. ICT has an impact on delivery of library and information science (LIS) educations. ICT has enable users to avail of the LIS professional changing from and intermediary to facilitator and enabler.

J.P. CHOUBEY CENTRAL LIBRARY SERVICES

S.N.	Services
1.	National digital library (NDL)
2.	DELNET membership and services
3.	Reprographic Services
4.	Reference Services
5.	Selective Dissemination Information (SDI)
6.	Current Awareness Services (CAS)
7.	Email Services
8.	Barcode Circulation
9.	E-Library Services
10.	Library Software
11.	Wi-Fi Library
12.	J-gate Engineering, J-gate Social and Management, Science
13.	Telephone
14.	Internet
15.	OPAC
16.	Study Book Services
17.	Resource Sharing
18.	On-Line Data Bases
19.	Multimedia Resource Services
20.	User Education Programme
21.	Printing Scanning Services

LIBRARY & DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE VISSION & MISION

VISION

- Vision to provide Information Technology based training program for university college and school library.
- Vision as a centre of intellectual enquiry the library of C V Raman University shares the aspiration to be the most dynamic learning environment in the state and continues to support professional growth and opportunity.
- Design and development of portal of knowledge management and knowledge E-learning.
- To provided training program on digital achieve.

LATEST TRENDS AND USE OF ICT IN FUNCTIONAL LIBRARY AND SERVICES

Bibliography services, digital library, E-library, virtual library, e-Journal, Web Technology, Administrative, Maintenance, Library consortia, Serial Control, circulation, Cataloguing, Classification, Web 2.0, Acquisition, Video Conferencing.

SYLLABUS

Syllabus of library and information science department has been proposed keeping in mind the recent trends in LIS and application of ICT in it following papers are included in the curriculum.

- Library And Society
 - Library Management
 - Library Classification
 - Reference and Information Sources
 - Library Cataloguing
 - Information Communicational and Society
 - Information Sources System and Services
 - Information Processing And Retrieval
 - Fundamental of Information Communication Technologies (ICT)
 - Preservation and Conversation of Library Material
 - Research Methodology
 - Academic Library System
 - Public Library System And Services
- Effective paper**
- dissertation
 - technical writing
 - archival Museum and archaeological information system

S.N.	Library Collection/Equipment	No. of Collection
1.	Books	50000
2.	Journals	80
3.	Magazine	Hindi - 29 English -24
4.	M.phil Thesis and dissertation	1237

5.	P.hd Thesis	106
6.	Hindi News Paper	11
7.	English News Paper	3
8.	Computer	23
9.	CC TV Camera	8
10.	Photo Copy Machine	1
11.	Printer	1
12.	Scanner	1
13.	National print journals	91
14.	Inter National print journals	21
15.	E-Books	670
16.	Project thesis	484
17.	Koha software	1

COURSES OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE EDUCATION

Library and information science department of Dr. C. V. Raman universities running following under Graduate / Post Graduate and Doctoral Programmes in Library and Information Science discipline.

1. **B.Lib**
2. **M.Lib**
3. **M.Phil**
4. **Ph.D**

MISSION

- Our mission to provide professional and knowledge for library science students we provide quality education to meet student's needs regardless of where the student lives instruction is of higher quality and placement to ensure that their educational experience is relevant and forward looking.
- Mission the library mission is to provided comparison resources and services in support of the research teaching and learning need of the university community.

UNIVERSITIES FACILITIES

Dr. C. V. Raman university is following facilities for different streams of education.

1. Radio Raman tools 94.3
2. BIO- GAS
3. Bus
4. Canteen
5. Herbal garden
6. Pradhan Mantry Kaushal Kendra (PMKK)
7. Wi-Fi campus
8. CCTV camera
9. Red Cross Society
10. Dispensary
11. Moot Court
12. NCC facilities
13. Girls / Boys Hostel and Mess
14. Bus Parking

15. Research Centre
16. Guest House
17. Central Library and e-library
18. Computer Labs
19. Digital Attendance
20. Biotech Park
21. Play Grounds
22. Laboratories
23. Bio Gas Plant
24. Girls Common Room
25. Conference Hall
26. Bank and ATM

OTHER ACTIVITIES

Educational Tour, NCC, NSS, Annual Sports, Placement, medical Awareness, National Seminar, Essay Compactions, Rangoli, Cultural Programme, Faculty development programme, Blood Donet Camp, Industrial Visit, Women Day Celebrations, Yoga Day Celebrations.

UNIVERSITY ACHIEVEMENTS

Over 70 Labs, Digital University, Institute of Open and Distance Education (IODE), Deen Dayal Upadhyay Kaushal Kendra Yojana, CVRU academy for Skill Development.

UNIVERSITY PUBLICATIONS

Journal Calendar, Diary, Pamplate, Magazines and browser.

CONCLUSIONS

Dr. C.V. Raman university aims to provide a high standard of liberal education to its student catering to their intellectual growth, as well as their holistic personality development which nurtures them to be responsible adults committed to high ethical standards.

Dr. C.V. Raman University through an innovative research based pedagogy with world the inspired, a plat term to Re-more.

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